

The reuse of bioarchaeology information

Survey Flow

Standard: The reuse of bioarchaeology information (1 Question)
Block: Consent and GDPR (6 Questions)
Standard: About you (6 Questions)
Standard: Do you publish data? (2 Questions)

Branch: New Branch

If

If Do you publish your data? No Is Selected

Block: Bioarchaeology community (3 Questions)
Standard: Block 7 (3 Questions)

EndSurvey:

Standard: About your data (18 Questions)
Standard: Process (4 Questions)
Standard: Bioarchaeology community (3 Questions)
Standard: Block 7 (3 Questions)

Page Break

Start of Block: The reuse of bioarchaeology information

Q1 Hello and thank you for taking time to complete this questionnaire.

Information about the project

Title of the study: The current and future reuse of bioarchaeological information

Supervisor: This dissertation is supervised by Jessica Hendy and Holly Wright in the department of archaeology at the University of York.

Description: As more and more bioarchaeological data is being curated, it is essential to ensure its accessibility to academics, researchers and the general public. As such, the main objective of this research project is to analyse the future of bioarchaeological research in terms of data reuse. This will be carried out in a multitude of ways. The first is an investigation via a needs analysis of a more standardised metadata standard and associated paradata for bioarchaeological terms. This needs analysis will also include a questionnaire to evaluate the current level of bioarchaeology data reuse. Currently, there is not one standardised metadata schema for bioarchaeological investigations, and the data is held within many different specialist archives, and the ability to reuse is extremely lacking. There may also prove to be scope to link the specialist reports of bioarchaeology to the site reports to ensure greater interoperability, and thus ensure accessibility to those who need it. Further through the capturing of paradata, the information created in individual projects will become more reusable.

Researcher: Alphaeus Lien-Talks, Digital Archaeology at the University of York

Methods of research: Written emails and questionnaire

Confidentiality, anonymity and data protection: Participants may withdraw from the project and withdraw their consent at any stage. A report on the results of the questionnaires and the relevant points from the email interviews will form one part of the undergraduate dissertation.

Respondents in the emails and questionnaire will be kept anonymous.

All email responses and questionnaire answers will be stored confidentially and digitally on the secure University Cloud Storage.

Results of the study: The outcomes of the questionnaires and interviews will be used in a published publication and will also be made available to participants through the publication of a simple report that can be emailed as well as form part of the research which can be emailed to you, if requested. Participants' will be also be offered an electronic copy of the questionnaire/interview section of the report.

If you have any questions or concerns, please contact Alphaeus Lien-Talks at AT1186@york.ac.uk.

End of Block: The reuse of bioarchaeology information

Start of Block: Consent and GDPR

Q2 Participant Name. If you wish to remain anomalous please feel free to leave it blank or write anon.

Q3 I consent to my participation in this project

Yes (1)

No (2)

Q4

I give permission for my questionnaire responses to be saved anonymously

Yes (1)

No (2)

Q5

I give permission for all questionnaire responses to be used in Alphaeus Lien- Talks' research

Yes (1)

No (2)

Q6 I give permission for all questionnaire responses to be used in a published article

Yes (1)

No (2)

Q7

Participants may withdraw from the project or the interview and withdraw their consent at any stage.

If you have any questions or concerns, please contact Alphaeus Lien-Talks at AT1186@york.ac.uk.

End of Block: Consent and GDPR

Start of Block: About you

Q8 What is your specialist area?

- aDNA (1)
 - Osteoarchaeology (2)
 - Palaeopathology (3)
 - Stable isotopes (4)
 - Zooarchaeology (5)
 - Palaeoproteomics (6)
 - Other (7) _____
-

Q9 What is your main institution?

Q10 In relation to which of the following do you collaborate with often? Tick all that apply

- aDNA (1)
 - Osteoarchaeology (2)
 - Palaeopathology (3)
 - Stable isotopes (4)
 - Zooarchaeology (5)
 - Palaeoproteomics (6)
 - Other (7) _____
-

Q11 Do you analyse publicly available data?

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
-

Display This Question:

If Q11 = 1

Q12 Rank the following in descending order of importance when analysing publicly available data. To rank, please click and drag each item to the desired order.

- _____ Site (1)
 - _____ Date (2)
 - _____ Methodology (3)
 - _____ Key results (4)
 - _____ Key images (5)
 - _____ Author's name(s) (6)
 - _____ Author's institution(s) (7)
 - _____ Provenance of sample (8)
 - _____ Equipment used (9)
 - _____ Any additional element? (10)
-

Q13 Do you have an ORCID account?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

End of Block: About you

Start of Block: Do you publish data?

Q14 Do you publish your data?

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
-

Display This Question:

If Q14 = 2

Q15 Why do you not publish your data?

- I am not sure how to (1)
- Economic reasons (2)
- I do not create data (3)
- It is unnecessary to (4)
- It requires too much time (5)

End of Block: Do you publish data?

Start of Block: Bioarchaeology community

Q16 On a scale of 1 to 7, in which 7 is extremely beneficial and 1 is unnecessary, how beneficial would it be to have the following?

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
To have a single repository for bioarchaeology data ()				4			
To link specialist reports to the fieldwork records ()				4			
To document paradata. Paradata contains information about the primary data collection process, including additional observational data. ()				4			
To have a single searchable interface for bioarchaeology data ()				4			

Q17 To what extent do you think the reuse of bioarchaeology information is important? Where 7 is essential and 1 is unnecessary.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
()				4			

Q18 Are there any further comments that you would like to make about the future of bioarchaeology data reuse?

End of Block: Bioarchaeology community

Start of Block: Block 7

Q19

Thank you for your answers so far. There is a chance that I would like to ask further questions in the future as the topic evolves. I would therefore like to ask permission to contact you again to ask these further questions.

Q20 Do you give permission for me to contact you again in the future?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Display This Question:

If Q20 = 1

Q21 Please write your email address so that I may contact you in the future

End of Block: Block 7

Start of Block: About your data

Q22 What data do you typically publish?

- Raw (1)
 - Partly processed (2)
 - Fully processed (3)
 - None (4)
-

Q23 Rank the following in descending order to what motivates you to deposit your own data. To do this, please click and drag items into your order of motivation.

- _____ Obligations to funding agency open access policy (1)
 - _____ Obligations to institution open access policy (2)
 - _____ To demonstrate biomolecular authenticity (3)
 - _____ For reviewers to replicate finding (4)
 - _____ For other researchers to replicate my findings (5)
 - _____ For other researchers to re-analyse data (6)
 - _____ To have access to my own data at a later stage (7)
-

Q24 In which format do you publish your data? Tick all that apply

- PDF (1)
 - Written document (14)
 - .DOCX (2)
 - .XLSX (3)
 - JPEG (4)
 - Comma separated value (CSV) (5)
 - Tab-separated values (TSV) (9)
 - JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) (10)
 - XML (11)
 - ZZL (13)
 - FASTQ (7)
 - .TXT (12)
 - BAM (8)
 - Other - please specify file type (6)
-

Q25 Where do you typically publish your data?

- Specialised repository (1)
- General repository (2)
- Institutional repository (3)
- In published report (4)
- Elsewhere (5) _____

Display This Question:

If Q25 = 2

Or Q25 = 1

Or Q25 = 3

Q26 What is the name of that repository?

Q27 Do you normally copyright data you generate in the course of your work?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

Display This Question:

If Q27 = 1

Q28 Under what licence do you normally list it?

- CC BY (1)
 - CC BY-NC (2)
 - CC BY-SA (3)
 - CC BY-ND (4)
 - CC BY-NC-SA (5)
 - CC BY-NC-ND (6)
 - Other (7) _____
-

Q29 Do you normally complete a data management plan?

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
-

Display This Question:

If Q29 = 1

Q30 To what extent do you believe the following are important to consider when making a data management plan? Where 7 is very important and 1 is completely unimportant

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Data summary ()	
Funding ()	
FAIR data. The FAIR Data Principles are a set of guiding principles in order to make data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. ()	
Allocation of resources ()	
Data security ()	
Ethical aspects ()	
Reusability of data ()	

Q31 Is your data typically open access?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

Display This Question:

If Q31 = 2

Q32 Do you think your data could be made open access?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

Display This Question:

If Q32 = 2

Q33 Why do you think this?

- Ethical (1)
 - Legal (2)
 - Financial - funding (3)
 - Financial - cost of research (4)
-

Q34 If you publish your research, is the raw data accessible from the reports?

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
 - I do not publish my research (3)
-

Q35 Do you think there is usually a good metadata schema for your work?

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
 - I am not sure (3)
-

Q36 Does your data have a persistent identifier?

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
 - I am not sure (3)
-

Q37 Do you know if any data you have generated in a report has been reused?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Display This Question:

If Q37 = 2

Q38 Would you like to know?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Q39 Do you systematically document your data? This involves the documenting of what is and is not in the file.

Yes (1)

No (2)

End of Block: About your data

Start of Block: Process

Q40 Briefly describe the process of data creation from first considering a research project, to documenting the experiment, to archiving or publishing.

Q41 On a scale of 1 to 7, how easy is this process? Where 7 is extremely easy and 1 is extremely difficult.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

()

Q42 Are there any issues which you come across whilst carrying out the process?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Q43 What are the principal challenges that you face whilst carrying out this procedure?

End of Block: Process
